

THE CONVERGENCE VALUE AND THE SIMPLE CONTINUED FRACTIONS OF SOME SMARANDACHE SEQUENCES

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Abstract . In this paper we consider the convergence value and the simple continued fraction of some Smarandache sequences.

Key words . Smarandache sequence , convergence value, simple continued fraction.

In [2] . Russo considered the convergence of the Smarandache series , the Smarandache infinite product and the Smarandache simple continued fractions for four Smarandache U -product sequences . Let $A=\{a(n)\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$ be a sequence of nonnegative numbers . In this paper we prove two general results as follows.

Theorem 1 . If $a(n) < a(n+1)$ for any n , then

$$\prod_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{a(n)} = \begin{cases} \infty , & \text{if } a(1)=0 , \\ 0 , & \text{if } a(1) \neq 0 . \end{cases}$$

Theorem 2 . If $a(n) > 0$ for any n with $n > 1$, then the simple continued fractions

$$a(1) + \frac{1}{a(2) + \frac{1}{a(3) + \dots}}$$

is convergent . Moreover , its value is an irrational number .

Proof of Theorem 1 . Under the assumption , the theorem is clear.

Proof of Theorem 2 . By [1, Theorems 161 and 166] ,

we obtain the theorem immediately .

Refernces

- [1] G. H. Hardy and E. M. Wright , An Introduction to the Theory of Numbers , Oxford University Press , Oxford , 1937 .
- [2] F. Russo , some results about four Smarandache U-product sequences, Smarandache Notions J. 11(2000), 42-49.

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